

d/d(ei/T) ln(p) as Probability Distributions in the Kaniadakis and Tsallis Cases Part 2: Cubic Distribution in ei/T

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 11, 2025

In Part i, we argued that for $k \ll 1$ or $ei/T \ll 1$ one could write: $d/d(ei/T) p(ei) = \exp(-k kei ei / (2T))$ ((1)) for the Kaniadakis case. This is keeping with a differential equation: $dp/d(ei/T) = -1/\sqrt{1+k kei ei / TT} p(ei)$ (see reference in Part 1). We suggested that in the Shannon-Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $d \ln(p) / d(ei/T) = 1$ and one could consider 1 as a certainty probability because $\ln(p) = -ei/T$ in all cases. We suggested that in the Kaniadakis case, one has instead a probability distribution (Gaussian) and in the Tsallis case, a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in ei/T instead of 1 for $d \ln(p) / d(ei/T)$. We also suggested that one could use these ideas in an a priori manner to derive the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions. We stated that this method should allow one to find further distributions. The objective here is to present one such different distribution, one which uses $k ei/T$ values to the power of 3 and is therefore an extension of the Kaniadakis result, we suggest.

Kaniadakis Case Revisited

The idea of Part 1 is to use;

$$d \ln(p) / d(ei/T) = \text{distribution}(ei/T) \quad ((1))$$

to derive a probability distribution $p(ei)$ based on the distribution one chooses. We suggested that a Gaussian applies in the Kaniadakis case. ((1)) applies for $k \ll 1$ or $ei/T \ll 1$, but the approach allows one to determine the full $p(ei)$ which holds for the range of k and ei/T values. The idea is that for $k \ll 1$ or $ei/T \ll 1$ one approaches the Maxwell-Boltzmann $\exp(-ei/T)$ while for $ei/T \gg 1$, one obtains a power law in ei/T .

We start with the notion of $\exp(-ei/T) = \exp(kx)$ power $1/k$ expanded to quadratic powers in ei/T . We let $-kei/T = x$.

Then;

$$p(x) = (1 + x + xx/2) \text{ power } 1/k \quad ((2)) \text{ for } k \ll 1 \text{ or } ei/T \ll 1$$

$$\text{Thus: } d \ln(p) / dx = (1+x) / \{1+x+.5xx\} \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Using a power series: } (1+x)\{1-x-.5xx+xx\} = 1- .5xx \quad ((4))$$

$$((4)) \text{ is equivalent to } 1/ \sqrt{1+xx} \quad ((5))$$

The Kaniadakis distribution then becomes:

$$p(x) = \{ x + \sqrt{1+xx} \} \text{ power } 1/k \text{ where } x=-kei/T \quad ((6))$$

((6)) holds for $0 < k < 1$ and all e_i/T not just in the $k \ll 1$ and $e_i/T \ll 1$ limits.

For $e_i/T \ll 1$ or $k \ll 1$, the polynomial in ((6)) is the second order representation of $\exp(-e_i/T)$, but ((5)) which specific form to use for non- $e_i/T \ll 1$, non- $k \ll 1$ cases.

New Distribution

We propose finding a new probability distribution based on the above ideas. This distribution must become $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ and a power law in e_i/T for $e_i/T \gg 1$. Instead of using the quadratic approach in x of the Kaniadakis approach, we consider a cubic one.

Then: $p(e_i) = \{1 + x + xx/2 + xxx/3\}$ power $1/k$ for $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ Here $x = -ke_i/T$ ((7))

$d \ln(p)/d(x)$ in this limit = $(1+x+xx/2) / \{1+x+xx/2 + xxx/6\}$ ((8))

= $1 - xxx/3$ approx= $1/ \text{cuberoot}(1+xxx)$ ((9))

We suggest that this implies a distribution of:

$p(e)$ unnormalized = $\{ -.5 + x + \sqrt{1+xx} + .5 \text{cuberoot}(\sqrt{1+xxx}) \}$ power $1/k$ ((10))

In the $e_i/T \gg 1$ limit one obtains a power law proportional to x power $1/k$ and in the $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, one obtains $\exp(-e_i/T)$ just as in the Kaniadakis case, but ((10)) is not the Kaniadakis distribution, although it is similar to it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we suggested that the $d \ln(p) / d(e_i/T) = \text{probability distribution}(e_i/T)$ in the $k \ll 1$ (or $q \text{ approx} = 1$ Tsallis case) or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limits yields both the Kaniadakis and Tsallis distributions for appropriate choices of a probability distribution. We suggested that a Gaussian applies for the Kaniadakis case and a Maxwell-Boltzmann for the Tsallis case. We suggested that other choices could lead to new distributions.

We noted in Part I, that in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ or $k \ll 1$ limit, $p(e)$ should represent a polynomial expansion of $\exp(kx)$ to the power $1/k$. The Kaniadakis case represents a quadratic expansion in x as shown in Part I. Here we consider a cubic expansion, i.e. use $p(x) = [1+x+xx/2 + xxx/6]$ power $1/k$. We calculate $d \ln(p) / dx$ in this $x \ll 1$ limit and find $1-xxx/3$. This is equivalent to an expansion of $1/ \text{cuberoot}(1+xxx)$. We thus suggest a new distribution (which is an extension of the Kaniadakis one) of:

$p(x) = [-.5 + x + \sqrt{1+xx} + .5 \text{cuberoot}(1+xxx)]$ power $1/k$

This becomes a power law proportional to x power $1/k$ in the $x \gg 1$ limit and $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the $k \ll 1$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit. Here $x = -ke_i/T$.